

Dilemmas in open publication practices

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Anna: would you publish in a super-prominent, career-making journal, at an outrageously high APC?

Finn: where would you publish work if you could choose between a novel open research platform, or in a highly visible journal?

Bob (& Betty): how can you engage in open science practices if your PhD supervisor is very hesitant about them?

Gretchen: would you opt for an expensive journal within an R&P deal, or a lower APC that you have to fund yourself?

Chiara: what to do when your funder does not cover publishing your chapter in open access in an edited volume that will be hybrid?

Harry: would you quit a prestigious editorship because of the publisher's not-so-open and practices and business model?

Dmitri & Darius: in international collaborations, could we attribute corresponding authorship just to make use of R&P deals?

Isa: could a junior researcher offer an open review on a paper by a prominent senior, in an uncertain career stage?

Evita: what if you want to publish with a niche publisher or outlet that does not (yet) offer open access options?

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Anna

Anna has a temporary appointment as an assistant professor at Leiden University. She has written an article that she believes can be published in *Nature*.

To meet the open access requirements of the funder of her research, Anna would need to pay *Nature's* article processing charge (APC) of €10,690. She could pay this APC from the project budget. As an alternative, Anna could publish her article in a disciplinary journal. These journals offer rigorous peer review and are well-read by the audience that Anna wants to reach. However, these disciplinary journals are typically seen as less prestigious than *Nature*. The APCs of these journals are three to ten times lower than the APC of *Nature*. Anna believes that publishing an article in *Nature* may be crucial to get a permanent position, at her current University or elsewhere. She is unsure whether she will get a permanent position if she opts to publish in a disciplinary journal. However, she feels uneasy about paying *Nature's* very high APC, also because she realizes that many researchers do not have access to the funds needed to pay such an APC.

Bob (& Betty)

Bob works as a PhD candidate at Leiden University. He attaches great importance to open science and insists on adhering to open science principles in his research.

Instead of publishing his articles in traditional academic journals, he wants to publish them on preprint servers and have their quality assessed through open peer review via Peer Community In (PCI), outside traditional academic journals. This process is not only transparent, but also completely free of publishing costs for Bob. Bob's supervisor Betty feels uncomfortable about this. She is a proponent of open access publishing but has never worked with PCI or similar services. Betty thinks that research should be made openly accessible in respected academic journals, in particular the work by junior contributors such as Bob. She is afraid that otherwise the research she works on with Bob will not be taken seriously, will not receive quality peer review, and will not reach the right audience. Betty thinks that eventually it could even negatively affect the standing of her institute if PhDs forego traditional publishing.

Chiara

Chiara's research project has been granted national funding that covers the costs of open access publishing. The funder has made immediate open access mandatory for all research results.

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Chiara's work has been accepted as a chapter in an edited volume. This is a real distinction in her field, as this book will be used by scholars as well as by professionals in training. Her chapter would appear alongside others on closely related topics, which will be authored by esteemed peers.

The publisher provides the option for Chiara to publish her chapter in open access at a reasonable cost, but as not all chapters of the volume will be made available in OA, Chiara's funder will not cover the costs of this type of publication. Chiara could publish her work as an article in an open access journal or repository instead. However, she is afraid she may not draw the same, mixed audience of peers and professionals that the publisher reaches; nor would the work benefit from evident connections to the other contributions.

Dmitri & Darius

Dmitri works as a post-doctoral researcher at Leiden University; Darius works in a similar position in Egypt.

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Neither has yet secured permanent employment. The two met during their PhD and regularly collaborate since. They currently have an article ready that they would submit to the hybrid Journal D. Dmitri's university has an R&P agreement with this journal's publisher; yet Darius' university does not. Darius has done half of the research and most of the writing and should therefore be the corresponding author, the pair decides. Unfortunately, Darius cannot come up with alternative funding for this publication, and the APCs are not waived by the publisher either. The pair have searched, but haven't found a similarly rigorous diamond open access journal, in which they could publish without any costs. They have thought of making the article freely available through the repository in Dmitri's institution, but hesitate whether such a paper will be recognised as published output in their annual performance interviews. As a last resort, the authors now consider appointing Dmitri as corresponding author, so that they can make use of Dmitri's university's agreement with the journal publisher.

Evita

Evita works at Leiden University, in a small research field in the Humanities. There is only one journal in her specific discipline in this field.

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It is the outlet of a Learned Society, produced in collaboration with a small, privately owned publishing company. This publisher does not yet support open access; the journal is subscription-based (also because the Society's annual budget depends on its subscribers). Evita wants to publish in this journal, as there are no alternatives of equal specificity and standing in her particular specialization. Yet she also wants to make her work openly available, in line with the University's open access commitment. She consults the University Library, for alternative routes. The Library advises Evita to look for preprint servers or open research platforms. Evita hesitates: she has never seen established peers in her field use such platforms. And will the publisher, also unfamiliar with this type of platform, still accept her work if it is available elsewhere?

Finn

Finn is the recipient of a Horizon Europe project grant, and in the second year of his project.

He wants to disseminate results in a research article, but he also has protocols and underlying data that he would like to share with peers. Finn knows his work is potentially groundbreaking, yet perhaps because of this also not uncontested. He therefore hesitates between publishing options available. Cost is not an issue, with his generous funding. Finn could go the traditional route of *Journal F*, a well-read, peer-reviewed journal in his field, produced by a large publisher. Peer review will be double-blind and rigorous, and Finn likely faces several rounds of revision. Yet once the article is accepted for publication, his peers will notice its appearance, for sure. Alternatively, Finn's Horizon grant gives him access to the exclusive platform Open Research Europe, where he can publish his paper and have it undergo post-publication review, for which he can suggest reviewers. The review process will be open, allowing Finn to engage in discourse with his reviewers. However, his peers are not alerted to his publication appearing on ORE, and may therefore not discover it.

Gretchen

Gretchen works at Leiden University. She has written an article that she would like to submit for publication in Journal G.

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This journal employs a gold open access publishing model. Moreover, it has a solid reputation in Gretchen's field, in particular because it advocates for advancing the reproducibility of research. It is published by a university press. The journal lists an APC of €1800. Gretchen does not have a budget to pay this APC and consults the University Library. The Library does not have a central budget for open access fees either. It therefore suggests Gretchen consider different journal titles, specifically those for which the University has a 'Read-and-Publish' agreement. The Library's information specialist suggests Journal Y, by Elsevier, or Journal Z, by Springer. Both journals have an APC just over €3000, but they are included in the agreement and therefore Gretchen can publish without extra cost. However, Gretchen would still rather publish in Journal G, because of its quality standards, as reproducibility is an issue of importance in her field.

Harry

Harry recently got appointed as an assistant professor at Leiden University.

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His editorship for *Journal H* was applauded in his hiring procedure, as this is an established international journal in his field. Authors can optionally publish in open access with this journal, if they pay an APC. Lately, *Journal H's* publisher has been pressuring the editorial board to accept more submissions. The publisher even pushes towards appointing extra editors of their own suggestion, without the current board's prior approval. Harry has never really liked the hybrid model with its APCs and is now particularly concerned about the loss of editorial autonomy.

Harry considers convincing his fellow editors to negotiate changes for *Journal H*, or perhaps even to move the journal to another publisher. That would require obtaining knowledge and mobilizing the community in his field. Yet he is hesitant to show this – let alone ask time and support for it – at the department where he newly arrived. Workload here is significant, and leadership has made clear that this editorship was a factor in hiring him in the first place. For this reason, he feels he cannot resign as an editor either.

Isa

Isa has recently started a project as a postdoctoral researcher at Leiden University.

During her PhD trajectory, getting her papers published in journals was a somewhat frustrating experience, with slow and arduous rounds of revision and resubmission. This got her interested in PRC-platforms, where authors can submit a paper, which is then, after a quick editorial check, published for open peer review. After reviewers' acceptance, the paper can get formally published through the platform or through an affiliate journal. Isa often checks relevant PRC platforms for new content. One PRC platform now contains an upload from a well-known, senior scholar in her field, working elsewhere in Europe. Isa is disappointed by the paper's quality: the methods section is unclear, and she thinks conclusions are not that well supported. This paper did not yet get any reviews. Isa is not invited to contribute a peer review for this paper, but she can volunteer to do so and demonstrate her substantial expertise on this topic. However, constructively formulating her feedback would take considerable time, and she hesitates to contribute a critical perspective on this established researcher's work – not in the least because she hasn't yet secured permanent employment...